

CHARACTERISATIONS OF HYBRID COMPOSITES

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1 Introduction

The addition of clay in oil palm fruit bunch (OPFB) fibre/PP composites [1] or also termed as hybrid composites showed an improvement on its tensile and flexural moduli. However the thermal degradation and water absorption behaviors of the composites have not been investigated yet. Besides mechanical properties, thermal degradation and water absorption behaviors of the composites are important information needed during material selection.

Clay presence in polymer composites was proven to enhance its thermal degradation behavior [2-4] which is strongly correlated with reduced oxygen permeability resulting from an elongated diffusion path. Meanwhile the effect of clay content on the water absorption behavior mainly contributed by the hydrophilic attributes of clay [5]. A study on the addition of clay in wood fiber composites also found out [6] the increased in decomposition temperature and melting temperature of the hybrid composites.

This report will investigate the effect of clay loading on the water absorption, thermal behaviour and impact strength of OPFB/PPnanoclay/PP hybrid composites.

2 Materials and Methods

2.1 Materials and Sample Preparation

Oil palm fruit bunch (OPFB) fibres were pulverised and screened to the size of 250 - 180 μm . Polypropylene pellets with 10 wt% of clay content (PPnanoclay) were supplied by Nanocor Inc (USA) meanwhile Polypropylene pellets

were manufactured by Petronas Malaysia Bhd (Malaysia). Maleic anhydride polypropylene (MAPP) manufactured by Sigma Aldrich Inc. (USA) was used as the coupling agent. The mixtures of PPnanoclay/PP were consisted of 10:100, 25:100, 40:100 and 100:100 by weight ratio. Those mixtures were filled with 20 wt% of OPFB and 2 wt% of MAPP as coupling agent to produce hybrid composites. The compounding was performed in a sigma blade thermal mixer at the temperature of 180°C. The samples were prepared by using MCP vertical injection moulding to produce test samples according to ASTM standard.

2.2 Composite Characterizations

Thermal analyses were carried out using a Perkin Elmer Instruments thermo gravimetric analyzer TGA. The tests were run in a nitrogen atmosphere from room temperature to 800°C with a heating rate of 10°C min⁻¹. Water-uptake measurements were performed by taking the weight (W_i) of all the specimens before being immersed in distilled water at room temperature of about 25°C. At regular interval samples were weighed (W_t) and prior to weighing the samples were carefully dried with soft cloth. The percentage of water uptake, M_t was determined using the following equation:

$$M_t(\%) = \frac{W_t - W_i}{W_i} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Thermal Degradation

The thermal degradation behaviour of hybrid composites with the increasing of PPnanoclay loading is shown in Fig.1. The presence of 20 wt% of OPFB in hybrid composites is indicated by the first shoulder. There is no significant different in the number of shoulders in TGA curves of composites without and with PPnanoclay loading despite that they were consist of different number of element. This is believed due to the lower clay content in the composites [2, 6, 7]. The decomposition temperature of hybrid composites has further increased as the PPnanoclay loading increase, this trend is also agreed by other literature [2, 7].

Fig. 1: TGA results on the effect of PPnanoclay in hybrid composites.

The increase of decomposition temperature as the PPnanoclay loading increase is believed due to the high aspect ratio of clay that act as heat barrier, which could enhance the overall thermal stability of the system as well as assisting in the formation of char after the thermal decomposition [8]. The char formation has also increased with the increasing of PPnanoclay loading.

3.2 Water Absorption Behaviour

The water absorption behaviour of hybrid composites shown in Fig. 2 indicates water saturation was reached after 150 days. The

figure also indicates that the addition of PPnanoclay has increased the water absorption ability of composites, which can be related to the hydrophilic nature of clay and OPFB fiber, thus the higher clay content the higher water absorption capability. Figure 3 shows the details of water absorption rate according to the number of day. Other factors contribute to the increase in water absorption capability such as microgaps and flaws at the interface between fibres and matrix due to poor bonding [9].

Fig. 2: The effects of PPnanoclay loading on the water absorption of hybrid composites.

Fig.3: Absorbed water according to the number of days.

3.3 Impact Strength

The effects of PPnanoclay loading on the impact strength of hybrid composites are shown in Fig.4. The addition of PPnanoclay in the composite has slightly increased the impact strength and has further increased with the increasing of PPnanoclay loading between 8% - 13% at 10 phr to 100 phr PPnanoclay loading.

The result suggests that the presence of clay has provided an alternative mechanism for energy dissipation in the hybrid composites. Several researchers [10, 11] believed that the increased in impact strength is an evidence of good interface bonding, however sometimes is not true [12] because there are many factors affecting the impact strength especially in hybrid composites where the direction of crack growth continually changes as it encounters particles. Furthermore, the fibres that are randomly oriented introduce complex stress concentrations regions [12, 13].

Fig.4: Effect of PPnanoclay loading on the impact strength.

3.3 Impact Fracture Surface

Fig. 5(a) and (b) show the fracture surfaces of composites at 0, 10 and 100 phr of PPnanoclay loading respectively. Comparing micrograph in Fig. 5 (b) and (c) observed no significant difference. This observation supported the result of the effect of PPnanoclay loading on the

impact strength of hybrid composites showed in Fig.4, which indicates small increase (5%) with the increasing of PPnanoclay loading from 10 to 100 phr.

Fig.5: Impact fracture surface of composites at (a) 0 phr, (b) 10 phr and (c) 100 phr of PPnanoclay loading.

However comparing micrographs in Fig. 5 (a) and (c) which is belong to the fracture surface of composites with and without clay content would recognize the difference. Fracture surface of composites without clay content shows smooth surface in the matrix region, whereas the matrix region for hybrid composites with 100 phr clay loading exhibits rougher surfaces. According to a literature [14], increasing fracture surface roughness can be used as evidence to prove crack deflection is occurring, which increases the crack length and therefore, increases the absorbed energy during deformation.

4 Conclusions

The thermal degradation and water absorption behaviours increased as the PPnanoclay loading increased. The impact strength of hybrid composite has slightly increased and further increase with the increasing of PPnanoclay loading.

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